

December newsletter

Hello and welcome. This month we spotlight open research at the University of Leicester and the work of LNL Dr Sarah Gunn. We have information about UKRN resources, upcoming UKRN webinars and workshops as well as some recommended reading and free training opportunities. Lots for you to share with your local network. Happy holidays!

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Please read on...and let us know what you think.

Spotlight on Leicester

Our recent [blog](#) spotlights open research at the University of Leicester and the work of the Local Network Lead Sarah Gunn. Learn about their open research activities and how to elicit gasps of horror from students. The Leicester Open Research Forum includes showcases where researchers share how they integrate open research practices into their own work. The focus is always on the idea that any small positive steps are a win, rather than aiming for perfect research from the beginning. This helps to encourage people new to open research into taking a first step, or getting more experienced people to try new things. Sarah would love to see preregistration being standard practice for students, as an achievable next step. She plans to try this with her clinical trainees and if it goes well, for this to be rolled out as a model more broadly at Leicester.

Read more [here](#)

Baseline survey prize draw winners

Thanks to all the LNLs who completed our baseline survey, we had 32 responses. As a reward we had 5 copies of Charlotte Pennington's 'A Student Guide to Open Science' to give away. The 5 winning LNLs were picked by UKRN office staff Kate Holmes and Will Gawned in a grand prize draw ceremony involving numbered pieces of paper and a small orange basket normally used as desktop tidy. The event was recorded for posterity, and this newsletter. Congratulations to LNLs Will Ball (Robert Gordon University), Alex Jones (Swansea University), Osama Mahmoud (University of Essex), Elena Piccardi (University of East London) and David Smailes (Northumbria University).

UKRN Resources

There is a [new table](#) on the UKRN website that lists a whole host of UKRN-created materials and resources including animations, videos, primers and training materials. It is now much easier to search for and find(!) resources to share with your local network.

UKRN Webinar

[Nurturing change through growing UKRN projects](#)

Thursday 18 January 2024 13:00 - 15:00

Making positive change in research culture isn't simple: it needs different strategies and approaches. UKRN is doing just that through a number of new projects. Our first webinar of the New Year is a great opportunity to hear about how we're nurturing changes in research culture through projects that work from the grassroots and across higher-level strategy. Find out how we are harnessing our community and reaching out beyond it, using strategies that range from using narrative theory to meta-research.

Speakers:

Neil Jacobs, Head of the UKRN's Open Research Programme

Anna Ploszajski, UKRN StoryArcs Story Associate

Will Gawned, Community Project Manager

Diane Hird, Community Project Co-ordinator

Lorna Duncan, Research Fellow STAR & METEOR

Rosalind Strang, Project Coordinator STAR & METEOR

LNL workshops

As part of the Community Project we are holding a series of workshops and webinars for LNLs throughout 2024.

Thursday 1st February 11:00 - 12:00

The first of these will be led by Kait Clark, LNL University of the West of England (UWE) and will be about setting up student consortia for undergraduate final year projects.

Please also add the following workshop dates and times to your diary:

- Thursday 7th March 13:00 - 14:00
- Thursday 4th April 13:00 - 14:00
- Thursday 2nd May 13:00 - 14:00

• Thursday 13th June 13:00 - 14:00

Further details to follow

Paper recommendation

[Eleven strategies for making reproducible research and open science training the norm at research institutions](#)

This 2023 multi-author eLife paper is the result of an online event organized in collaboration with the [German Reproducibility Network](#). As the title suggests it offers 11 strategies for reproducible research and open science training. These cover research assessment criteria, training and community building.

Read more [here](#)

Free Responsible Research webinars

[Responsible Research in Practice](#) is a UKRN affiliate stakeholder and is part of the Stakeholder Engagement Group. The company was founded by Dr Nikki Osborne in 2015 and provides training and consultancy on improving practices and promoting a good research culture for a range of academic, commercial and other life science research organisations around the world. They provide FREE 1-hour Responsible Research webinars covering a range of topics. More info [here](#)

Dorothy Bishop Prize

Celebrating the contribution of Early Career Researchers to research improvement.

Have you, or someone you know, achieved or contributed something special to improve research or promote open research practices? UKRN are seeking nominations for the Dorothy Bishop Prize, which recognises and rewards the achievements of Early Career Researchers. Find out more [here](#)

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing. Would you like to be a guest editor? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

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